

Review

Selenium-Enriched Lactic Acid Bacteria: Functional Characteristics and Application Potential Research Progress

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Selenium (Se) is an essential trace element for the human body, and its physiological functions, such as antioxidant activity, immune regulation, and anticancer properties, have been widely recognized. Microbial-mediated Se biotransformation can convert highly toxic inorganic Se into low-toxicity, highly bioavailable organic Se forms. Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) have emerged as particularly effective in Se enrichment and transformation, due to their high Se tolerance, unique Se metabolic pathways, and probiotic properties. This paper provides a comprehensive review of the current research on the Se tolerance and enrichment capacity of LAB, their mechanisms of Se-enrichment, nutritional value, and bioactivity. It also explores their potential applications in fermented foods and the pharmaceutical industry.

Keywords: Selenium-enriched; Lactic acid bacteria; Bioactivity; Fermented foods

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Introduction

Selenium (Se) is a core component of antioxidant enzymes such as glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px) and plays a key role in antioxidant, immune-regulating, and anticancer functions (Lu et al., 2024). Globally, approximately 1.5 billion people face insufficient Se intake. In China, 72% of the soil has Se levels below the international standard (0.1 mg/kg), which has led to a high incidence of diseases such as Keshan disease and thyroid dysfunction (Minich, 2024). Traditional Se supplementation relies on inorganic Se (e.g., sodium selenite), which is highly toxic and has low bioavailability. In contrast, microorganisms can metabolize inorganic Se into organic Se compounds (e.g., selenomethionine and selenoproteins) or elemental Se nanoparticles (SeNPs), significantly reducing toxicity and enhancing bioactivity (Xu et al., 2020).

Lactic acid bacteria (LAB), recognized as generally recognized as safe (GRAS) probiotics, combine the functions of Se-enrichment and probiotic activity. In terms of physiological characteristics, the growth and metabolic conditions of LAB (such as growth temperature and pH value) closely resemble the human environment. Additionally, the population density of probiotics in LAB can reach an ideal high concentration in a given volume, ensuring their high survival rate in the harsh human gastrointestinal tract. Therefore, LAB are an ideal carrier for the development of new Se supplements. In recent years, research on the conversion of inorganic Se to organic Se by LAB has been widely valued and recognized. For example, the high-fat diet supplemented with Se-enriched LAB significantly improved the health indicators of the mice when adding LAB, sodium selenite, and Se-enriched LAB were respectively to a high-fat diet and fed to mice (Zhou et al., 2021). A freeze-dried Se-enriched LAB powder (containing 150 µg of Se per gram) was used in an intervention study targeting Se-deficient individuals, and the results showed that plasma Se levels increased by 42% (Wang et al., 2024). After 48 hours of fermentation by *Lactobacillus acidophilus* 336636, *L. plantarum* 336421, and *L. delbrueckii* subsp.187941, the ability to convert inorganic Se into SeCys₂ in defatted Se-enriched rice bran increased by 49%, 42%, and 49%, respectively (Zhang et al., 2023). Therefore, developing Se-enriched foods using Se-enriched LAB can provide an efficient and safe way to supplement Se for individuals with Se deficiency. However, current research still faces some bottlenecks, such as poor strain stability, high industrialization costs, and safety controversies. This article systematically summarizes the research progress of Se-enriched LAB to provide strategic support for breaking through the above-mentioned bottlenecks and to provide theoretical support for the development of functional foods and clinical transformation.

Selenium Tolerance and Enrichment Capacity of LAB

The Se-enrichment capacity of LAB is closely related to their Se tolerance. Different scholars have employed various methods to screen for strains with high Se tolerance. For example, the growth curves of 4 LAB strains, including *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Bifidobacterium animalis*, *Lactobacillus plantarum* and *Streptococcus thermophilus*, were determined in a culture media containing 0–1000 mg/kg sodium selenite and the results showed that *Lactobacillus acidophilus* had the strongest Se enrichment capacity, with a Se content of 13,039.62 mg/kg in its freeze-dried powder (Chen et al., 2024). The Se-enrichment rates of 9 strains of LAB were compared in a medium containing 50 µg/mL sodium selenite. It was found that *Lactobacillus plantarum* ZW107 had the highest Se-enrichment rate (65.63%), and scanning electron microscopy revealed the formation of elemental Se particles on its surface (Hu et al., 2024). 8 strains of Se-enriched LAB, including *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus*, and *Lactobacillus casei*, were selected to compare their Se tolerance and Se-enrichment capabilities. Some of these strains were able to survive in a medium containing 500 µg/mL sodium selenite. A combined UV and diethyl sulfate mutagenesis method was applied to the superior Se-enriching strains, ultimately yielding a mutant strain, *Lactobacillus plantarum* Dfa-301-30, with high biomass and high Se content. (Wang, 2024).

Moreover, culture conditions, including Se addition amount, Se addition time, pH, and culture time, significantly affect the Se-enrichment capacity of LAB. Optimizing these conditions can markedly improve the Se-enrichment efficiency of LAB. As a result, several researchers have focused on optimizing the Se-enrichment conditions for strains with strong Se-enriching abilities. For example, Chen et al. optimized the process of *Lactobacillus paracasei* using Box-Behnken design and determined the optimal conditions: a Se content of 5844.22 mg/kg in the bacterial strain, a Se addition amount of 2.07 mg/kg, a Se addition time of 5.76 h, and a final Se content of 14002.96 mg/kg (Chen et al., 2024). Similarly, Wang used a Box-Behnken design to optimize the Se-enrichment conditions for the mutant strain *Lactobacillus plantarum* Dfa-301-30, which has high biomass and high Se content. The optimal conditions were a sodium selenite concentration of 5.0 µg/mL, Se addition time of 7.6 hours, initial pH of 5.5, inoculation amount of 3.0%, and culture duration of 36.0 hours. The Se content of this strain reached 839.635 mg/kg, which is 1.77 times higher than before optimization (Wang, 2024). Dong screened a strain of *Enterococcus faecium* with strong Se-enrichment ability from the pedicels of *Hovenia dulcis*, which was suitable for fermenting *Hovenia dulcis* juice. It was found that when the culture time was 3, 15, and 21 h, the strain was in the logarithmic growth phase, stationary phase, and degradation phase, respectively. The growth condition of the strain was good when the culture time was 15–18 h, and the Se-enrichment rate could reach 39.06% under the optimal conditions (Dong et al., 2019). After summarizing and analyzing the Se conversion rates and Se-enrichment trends of different LAB strains, it was found that there are differences in the Se-enrichment abilities among different microorganisms, as shown in Table 1.

Tab.1 Comparison of Selenium Tolerance and Enrichment Capacities of Different LAB Strains

Strain Name	Se-Enrichment Capacities	reference
<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i> subsp. GXB032	At 10 µg/mL sodium selenite and 3 h addition time, 5 strains achieved >375 µg/g dry biomass in total and organic Se content, with >95% organic Se conversion rate	Zhu et al. 2025
<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i> GXB083		
<i>Leuconostoc lactis</i> GXB059		
<i>Weissella cibaria</i> GXB053		
<i>Lactobacillus brevis</i> GXB065		
<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i> L123	with or without Se-enrichment tolerated 0.5% bile salt with survival rates above 80%	Liao et al., 2024
<i>Lactococcus lactis</i> L126		
<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i> ZHL-2	Se-enrichment rate 85.46%	Zhang et al. 2024
<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i> 21805	Growth inhibited at 20 µg/mL Se; Se content reached 4.88 ± 0.39 mg/g at 10 µg/mL Se	Zan et al., 2024
<i>Lactobacillus paracasei</i> 20241		
<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i> 21828		
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> 23185		
<i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i> 6064		
<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i> 6076	Se content 23.08, 8.62 和 8.51 mg/g, respectively	Shokoufeh et al., 2023
<i>Lactobacillus animalis</i>		
<i>Lactobacillus gallinarum</i>		
<i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i>	Se-enrichment rate 81.80%	Wei et al., 2021
<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i> JX5		

Se-Enrichment Mechanism of LAB

The mechanism of Se-enrichment in LAB is a multi-step process involving the uptake, reduction, bioconversion, storage, efflux, and metabolic regulation of Se. These steps work together to determine the efficiency of Se-enrichment and the types of products formed in LAB. The mechanism of Se-enrichment in LAB is a complex process of biotransformation, mainly including the following key steps:

1)Selenium Uptake LAB take up inorganic Se (such as selenite, Na₂SeO₃) into the cell through transport proteins on the cell membrane. These transport proteins may be similar to phosphate or sulfate transport systems because the chemical properties of inorganic Se are similar to those ions. The permeability of the cell membrane and the activity of the transport proteins are important factors affecting the efficiency of Se uptake.

2)Selenium Reduction The inorganic Se taken up into the cell is reduced to organic Se or elemental Se. This process usually involves the intracellular reductase system, such as NADH-dependent reductases or glutathione reductase (GR). The activity of reductases and the intracellular reducing environment (such as the glutathione/GSSG ratio) are crucial for Se reduction.

3)Selenium Bioconversion The reduced Se can be further converted into organic Se compounds, such as selenoamino acids (such as selenocysteine and selenomethionine) or selenoproteins. This process involves the participation of multiple enzymes, such as cysteine desulfurase and methionine synthase. The activity of enzymes and the intracellular metabolic pathways determine the efficiency of Se bioconversion and the types of products formed.

4)Selenium Storage The bioconverted Se is stored in the cell in various forms, such as selenoamino acids, selenoproteins, or Se nanoparticles (SeNPs). The formation of Se nanoparticles may be related to the self-aggregation of Se metabolic products within the cell. The form of Se storage affects its stability and bioavailability.

5)Selenium Efflux Part of the Se may be expelled from the cell through efflux pumps on the cell membrane to maintain Se balance within the cell. This process may involve ATP-dependent efflux pumps or membrane channel proteins. The activity of efflux pumps and the intracellular Se concentration are key factors affecting Se efflux.

The processes of Se uptake, reduction, bioconversion, storage, and efflux are regulated by multiple intracellular signaling pathways, such as redox status, nutrient availability, pH, and temperature. The intracellular signaling network and transcription factors play important roles in regulating Se metabolism.

Bioactivity of Se-Enriched LAB

Antioxidant Activity During the body's own metabolic processes, free radicals are produced. A normal amount of free radicals in the body will not harm the organism, but an excess of free radicals can disrupt the body's internal balance, accelerate aging, and even cause diseases. LAB and Se both have good antioxidant properties, and Se-enriched LAB can effectively scavenge free radicals and reduce oxidative stress, with better effects than ordinary LAB. Zhu discovered that the DPPH, superoxide anion, and ABTS free radical scavenging rates of Se-enriched *Lactobacillus mucosae* GXB083 were the best, with scavenging rates of 43.64%, 19.24%, and 21.51%, respectively (Zhu et al., 2025). Hu found that after Se-enrichment, the superoxide anion scavenging rate of *Lactobacillus plantarum* ZW107 increased by 11.67%, and the hydroxyl radical scavenging rate increased by 11% (Hu et al., 2023). At the same time, Se-enriched LAB have synergistic antioxidant effects with plant-derived polyphenols. The total phenolic and flavonoid contents in fermented grape juice increased by 13.9% and 18.2%, respectively, the ABTS free radical scavenging rate increased from 50.16% to 63.23%, and the ferric ion reducing power increased by 17.7% (from 0.682 to 0.803) (Zhai et al., 2023). Khan found through animal experiments that oral administration of Se-enriched probiotic preparations (*Lactobacillus acidophilus*) could reduce the content of malondialdehyde and increase the activities of glutathione, glutathione peroxidase, and superoxide dismutase (Khan et al., 2019). These studies have confirmed that Se combined with certain organic substances can enhance their antioxidant activity.

Antibacterial Activity Some pathogenic microorganisms, such as *Escherichia coli*, *Candida albicans*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*, can cause a variety of diseases. Se-enriched LAB have significant inhibitory effects on pathogenic bacteria. Zhang reported that after Se-enrichment, the diameter of the inhibition zone of *Lactobacillus plantarum* ZHL-2 increased by 1.14–2.89 mm. The antibacterial peptides secreted by it work synergistically with Se to disrupt the cell membranes of pathogenic bacteria (Zhang et al., 2024). Zamare found that Se nanoparticles obtained from different *Lactobacillus* strains after Se-enrichment showed increasing antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Candida albicans* with increasing Se nanoparticle concentration. Among them, the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of *Lactobacillus* SeNPs against *Staphylococcus aureus* was 50 µg/mL (Zamare et al., 2018). In addition, Kheradmand found that Se-enriched *Lactobacillus* fermentation broth could inhibit the growth of *Candida albicans* and reduce Se dioxide to elemental Se nanoparticles in the bacterial cells. Compared with non-Se-enriched bacterial cells, elemental Se nanoparticles significantly reduced the number of *Candida albicans* (Kheradmand et al., 2014). In summary, both Se-enriched products of LAB and the bacterial cells themselves can exert antibacterial effects.

Anticancer and Immune Regulation Se mainly exerts anticancer and immune-regulating functions in the body in the form of selenoproteins, selenopolysaccharides, and Se nanoparticles. For example, He et al. found that selenoproteins such as selenoprotein P (SeP), glutathione peroxidase (GPx), thioredoxin reductase (TXNRD), and selenoprotein F (SEP15, SeF) can influence the occurrence and progression of tumors by modulating cancer-related signaling pathways (He et al., 2025). Alduais et al. discovered that selenium nanoparticles (SeNPs) can selectively induce apoptosis in various types of cancer cells while protecting normal somatic cells from damage. Moreover, SeNPs have been shown to possess antioxidant and immune-regulatory capabilities, which can enhance the tumor-killing abilities of NK cells, $\gamma\delta$ T cells, and CIK cells (Alduais et al., 2025). Jin et al. found that selenium-containing polysaccharides can enhance the body's immune response by regulating the activity of immune cells, thereby inhibiting tumor growth and spread. In addition, selenium polysaccharides can protect cells from oxidative damage by scavenging reactive oxygen species (ROS) and regulating redox balance (Jin et al., 2025). In addition, the immune activity is one of the most significant biological activities of polysaccharides, and Se also significantly affects the immune system of the body. More and more pharmacological and clinical studies have shown that edible mushroom selenopolysaccharides can regulate and enhance cell immune functions by promoting the production of cytokines and affecting cell signal transduction (Yao et al., 2024). Studies have shown that selenopolysaccharides can stimulate immune cells to release cytokines such as interleukin (IL), interferon (INF), and tumor necrosis factor (TNF) to exert their functions. Yang found that Se-enriched *Lactobacillus acidophilus* activated the NF- κ B pathway in macrophages and enhanced the secretion of IL-6 and TNF- α (Yang et al., 2009). Kang et al. found that the administration of selenium-enriched *Lactobacillus plantarum* significantly increased the metabolism of selenocysteine, selenocystathionine, and selenomethionine, as well as plasma selenium levels and anti-oxidant capability in mice (Kang et al., 2020).

Applications of Se-Enriched LAB

Fermented Foods Se-enriched LAB are mainly applied in Se-enriched fermented foods, which have satisfactory sensory characteristics, high nutritional value, and health-promoting features. They have received widespread attention and recognition internationally. Deng added *Lactobacillus brevis* to yogurt, increasing the Se content to 24 mg/kg, extending the shelf life by 20%, and maintaining a live bacterial count of $>1 \times 10^7$ CFU/g during storage (Deng et al., 2015). Shu added

Se-enriched *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* to goat milk powder to make Se-enriched goat milk tablets. The predicted shelf life of these tablets was 406 days, and the bioavailability of Se was increased by three times (Shu et al., 2020). Zhai added sodium selenite to skim milk and fermented grape juice with a mixture of *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus thermophilus* (1:1). The Se content in the grape juice increased by 157%, the sensory score reached 88.3 points, and the retention rate of phenolic substances during storage was >90% (Zhai et al., 2023). Zuo used Se-enriched *Lactobacillus plantarum* to ferment composite fruit and vegetable juice, increasing the polyphenol content by 15% and the antioxidant capacity (ORAC value) by 40% (Zuo et al., 2021). In summary, the application of Se-enriched LAB in fermented foods not only increases their nutritional value but also enhances their functional characteristics.

Pharmaceutical Field LAB themselves have multiple biological functions, such as promoting intestinal health and enhancing immunity. The anticancer, antioxidant, liver-protecting, and immune-enhancing functions of Se combine with the biological functions of LAB, making Se-enriched LAB more advantageous in preventing diseases and promoting health (Zhou et al., 2022). For example, Wang et al. proved that intake of selenium-enriched *L. plantarum* ZZU 8–12 upregulated the abundance of short-chain fatty acid-producing genera including *Lactiplantibacillus*, *Phascolarctobacterium*, *Butyricoccus*, and *Clostridiales* bacterium in fecal microbiota and thus inhibited ALI induced by CCL4 injection in mice (Wang et al., 2025). Qiu found that Se-enriched *Bifidobacterium longum* alleviated 5-FU-induced chemotherapy-induced mucositis in normal mice, with a recovery rate of 80% (Qiu et al., 2017).

Conclusions and Prospects

Se-enriched LAB combine Se supplementation with probiotic functions and have broad prospects in the fields of functional foods and pharmaceuticals. LAB convert inorganic Se into highly bioactive SeCys, SeMet, and SeNPs through thiol-mediated reduction, enzyme-catalyzed reduction, and SeNPs assembly pathways. Their products show outstanding performance in antioxidant activity, antibacterial activity, anticancer activity, and immune regulation. Currently, Se-enriched LAB have been successfully applied in functional foods such as fermented dairy products and dietary supplements, and have shown potential in relieving enteritis, liver injury, and other diseases.

However, large-scale production faces challenges such as high costs (Se source prices, freeze-drying processes) and poor strain stability. There is still controversy regarding safety. Although organic Se has lower toxicity, excessive intake (>400 µg/d) can still lead to hair loss and neurological damage. Therefore, it is necessary to establish precise dose–effect models and verify long-term safety through animal experiments. Many studies have confirmed that Se nanoparticles have strong activity, low toxicity, and good absorption, and can be used as a new form of Se supplementation. However, many internal reduction mechanism issues, such as the key genes, enzymes, or proteins involved in Se nanoparticle formation, the pathways for Se entry into LAB, and their transport mechanisms, still need continuous research.

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References

- [1] Lu JH, Yang CX. Advances in the bioactivity of selenium-enriched products from microbial fermentation. *Food and Fermentation Industries*, 2024; 50 (21):357-365.
- [2] Minich WB. Selenium Metabolism and Biosynthesis of Selenoproteins in the Human Body. *Biochemistry (Moscow)*, 2022; 87 (Suppl 1):S168-S177.
- [3] Xu Y, Wu S, He J, He C, Wang P, Zeng Q, Yang F. Salt-induced osmotic stress stimulates selenium biotransformation in *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* ATCC 53103. *Lwt*. 2020; 131:109763.
- [4] Zhou M, Zheng X, Zhu H, Li L, Zhang L, Liu M, Liu Z, Peng M, Wang C, Li Q, Li D. Effect of *Lactobacillus plantarum* enriched with organic/inorganic selenium on the quality and microbial communities of fermented pickles. *Food chemistry*. 2021; 365:130495.

- [5] Wang RN, Li JY, Lu YY, L M, Ma WL, Zhao XB. Research progress on selenium enrichment mechanism and selenized product characteristics of lactic acid bacteria. *Food and Fermentation Industries*, 2024; 50(15):1-10.
- [6] Zhang JN, Zhang XX, Wang DM, Zhao GH, Yu JL, Lei L. Improvement of Antioxidant Activity of Defatted Selenium-Enriched Rice Bran by Lactic Acid Bacteria Fermentation. *Food Science*, 2023; 44(24):146-154.
- [7] Chen D, Cao YL, Liu WY, Miao MY, Bi XH, W SQ. Preparation of Selenium Enriched Lactic Acid Bacteria. *Food Industry*, 2024; 45(03):53-56.
- [8] Hu LJ, Cao YL, Chen XD, X T, Zhou YC. Research on Selenium-enriched Ability of Lactic Acid Bacteria and Its Antioxidant Capacity in vitro. *Journal of Sichuan University of Science & Engineering (Natural Science Edition)*, 2023; 36(06):26-33.
- [9] Wang YX. Screening of selenium-enriched lactic acid bacteria and research on selenium-enriched fermentation process. Master's thesis. Harbin University of Commerce, Harbin, 2017.
- [10] Chen FF, Li HY, Sun JZ, Yin HQ. Screening of Selenium-Rich Lactic Acid Bacteria and Research on Selenium-Rich Process. *Food Science and Technology*, 2024; 49(7):40-48.
- [11] Dong XF, Hu ZQ, Wei JP, Yuan YH, Yue TL. Screening of lactic acid bacteria with strong selenium enriched ability from *Hovenia dulcis* peduncles. *Food Science and Technology*, 2019; 44(5):8-14.
- [12] Zhu H, Yu L, Li F, Su XY, Qin Y, Liu XL, Wang CH. Screening and in Vitro Activity Comparison of Selenium-enriched Lactic Acid Bacteria from Plants in Bama Region of Guangxi. *Modern Food Science and Technology*, 2025; 41(4):1-14.
- [13] Liao JJ, Tan CY, Liang L, Luo YZ, Li HL, Chen YY, Pei XD, Wang CH. Screening and identification of selenium-enriched purine-lowering *Lactobacillus plantarum* and *Lactococcus lactis* with high stress tolerance and antioxidant capacity. *Food Bioscience*, 2024; 60:1044399.
- [14] Zhang YF, Lu XR, Wu WY, Bai FL, Cui WC, Shan XQ, Li JR, Li YM. Screening of Selenium-Rich Lactic Acid Bacteria from Intestinal Tract of Aquatic Products and Evaluation of Its Bioactivities in vitro. *Food Research and Development*, 2024; 45(18):106-113.
- [15] Zan LX, Chen Z, Zhang B, Zou XY, Lan AF, Zhang WY, Yuan YH, Yue TL. Screening, Characterization and Probiotic Properties of Selenium-Enriched Lactic Acid Bacteria. *Fermentation*, 2024; 10(1): 39.
- [16] Norouzi S, Daneshyar M, Farhoomand P, Tukmechi A, Tellez-Isaiasc G. In vitro evaluation of probiotic properties and selenium bioaccumulation of lactic acid bacteria isolated from poultry gastrointestinal, as an organic selenium source. *Research in Veterinary Science*. 2023; 162:104934.
- [17] Wei MT, Wang Y, Shan CJ, Liu XL, Xia XD, Dong MS, Zhou JZ. Screening of Selenium-enriched Lactic Acid Bacteria and Evaluation of Their Bioactivities in Vitro. *Science and Technology of Food Industry*, 2021; 42(8):102-108.
- [18] Zhai SL, Wang Y, Zhang XF. Study on the process conditions and functional components of selenium-enriched lactic acid bacteria fermented grape juice. *Agriculture and Technology*, 2023; 43(20):16-19.
- [19] Khan AZ, Khan IU, Khan S, Afzal S, Hamid M, Tariq M, Hap I, Ulah N, Khan MA, Bilal S, Huang K, Liu R. Selenium-enriched probiotics improve hepatic protection by regulating pro-inflammatory cytokines and antioxidant capacity in broilers under heat stress conditions. *J Adv Vet Anim Res*, 2019; 6(3):355-361.
- [20] Zamare DK, Mishra B. Enhanced antimicrobial activity of probiotics through selenium nanoparticles enrichment against gastrointestinal pathogens. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 2018, 9(2):738-742.
- [21] Kheradmand E, Rafii F, Yazdi MH, Sepahi AA, Shahverdi AR, Oveisi MR. The antimicrobial effects of selenium nanoparticle-enriched probiotics and their fermented broth against *Candida albicans*. *DARU Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2014; 22:1-6.
- [22] He L, Zhang L, Peng Y, He Z. Selenium in cancer management: exploring the therapeutic potential. *Frontiers in Oncology*, 2025;1 4:1490740.
- [23] Alduais MA, El Rabey HA, Mohammed GM, Al-Awthan YS, Althiyabi AS, Attia ES, Rezk SM, Tayel AA. The anticancer activity of fucoidan coated selenium nanoparticles and curcumin nanoparticles against colorectal cancer lines. *Scientific Reports*, 2025; 15(1):287.
- [24] Jin K, Shi S, Huang D, Huang H, Zou B, Huang W, Chen T. Maintaining cardiac homeostasis by translational selenium nanoparticles with rapid selenoproteins regulation to achieve radiation-induced heart prevention. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 2025; 27:160005.
- [25] Yao P, Shi LW, Fan JR, Zhang YX, Yue TL, Guo H. Research Progress on Absorption and Transformation Mechanism and Biological Function of Selenium-enriched Edible Fungi. *Science and Technology of Food Industry*, 2024; 45(16):439-450.
- [26] Yang J, Huang K, Qin S, Wu X, Zhao Z, Chen F. Antibacterial action of selenium-enriched probiotics against pathogenic *Escherichia coli*. *Digestive diseases and sciences*, 2009; 54:246-254.

- [27] Kang S, Li R, Jin H, You H, Ji G. Effects of selenium- and zinc-enriched *Lactobacillus plantarum* SeZi on antioxidant capacities and gut microbiome in an ICR mouse model. *Antioxidants*, 2020; 9:1028.
- [28] Deng Y, Man C, Fan Y, Wang Z, Li L, Ren H, Cheng W, Jiang Y. Preparation of elemental selenium-enriched fermented milk by newly isolated *Lactobacillus brevis* from kefir grains. *International Dairy Journal*, 2015; 44:31-36.
- [29] Shu G, Mei S, Chen L, Zhang B, Guo M, Cui X, Chen H. Screening, identification, and application of selenium-enriched *Lactobacillus* in goat milk powder and tablet. *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation*, 2020; 44(6): e14470.
- [30] Zuo YP, Sun GY, Zhang L. Influence of selenium-enriched lactic acid bacteria on the quality of composite fruit and vegetable juice. *Food Research and Development*, 2021; 42 (14): 36-42.
- [31] Zhou J, Zhang D, Lu X, Liu X, Xu W, Chen L, Cai J, Din ZU, Cheng S. Green synthesis of robust selenium nanoparticles via polysaccharide–polyphenol interaction: design principles and structure–bioactivity relationship. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering*, 2022; 10(6):2052-2062.
- [32] Wang, YP, Ma, HY, Li, HL, Huang YH, Tang YP, Tang XX, Sun PT, Tan ZF, Pang HL, Yang FY. Selenium-Enriched *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* ZZU 8–12 Regulates Intestinal Microbiota and Inhibits Acute Liver Injury. *Probiotics & Antimicro. Prot.*, 2025; 1-13.
- [33] Qiu YS, Ji R, Shao L, Chen DJ, Tan J. Preventative effects of selenium-enriched *Bifidobacterium Longum* on 5-fluorouracil-induced intestinal mucositis in mice. *Industrial Microbiology*, 2017; 47(04):19-23.

